

**COMBINATION OF SIGNIFICANT HISTORICAL LEXEMAS IN THE
SEMANTIC FIELD**

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Annotation: This article discusses the importance of lexemes representing certain symbols in the historical discourse, as well as the method of using historical words in the novels of the writer Muhammad Ali, his unique approach to word selection. Factual materials on historical words are taken from Muhammad Ali's novels "Warlords" (S.) and "Ulug' sultanat" (U.s.).

Key words: historical discourse, archaism, historicism, language levels, semantic field.

It is known that historical words in the language system, as a separate group of linguo-cultural language units, are an important source that reflects the cultural values of the nation specific to a certain period, ethnic, socio-cultural views, traditions, customs and customs, dress culture, manners, communication etiquette norms of the nation. The direction of our research is focused on the linguistic reflection of historical words in the Uzbek historical discourse and the identification, definition and description of the linguistic peculiarities of these units.

In world linguistics, the study of the linguistic landscape of the world in the directions of cognitive linguistics, linguocultural science, and sociolinguistics has become widespread. Ethno-cultural features of language units, definition of the theoretical and methodological principles of classification of the world scene require consistent and systematic research. It remains one of the important tasks to examine the concept of the landscape of the world from different angles, to determine the linguistic and non-linguistic factors in the formation of a conceptual system of multifaceted cognitive-stylistic possibilities that reflect its specific features.

Periodization is one of the most important issues in the study of language history. The history of the development of the Uzbek literary language is divided by most linguists into different periods - stages. Each period is interpreted on the basis of phonetic, lexical, grammatical aspects of the language. One of the historical stages of the Uzbek literary language - the lexical-semantic and grammatical features typical of the old Uzbek literary language - are clearly visible in Muhammad Ali's novels "Sarbadorlar" and "Ulug' Saltanat". The writer skillfully used the lexical units, syntactic devices, and grammatical forms of the old Uzbek language in order to embody the historical truth before the eyes of the reader, to show the

historical national color of the Uzbek people. The writer effectively used historical lexical units to ensure and reveal historical reality in his novels, and the historical lexemes in them belong to several "nests" according to word groups and their semantic groups.

In other words, lexemes within a word group are divided into certain semantic "nests" according to their lexical-semantic characteristics, in addition to being united within the group. From this point of view, it is appropriate to classify historical words on this basis.

Historical words and terms are widely used in the novel, where each word - lexeme unites around a specific theme and forms a specific microfield. Because there may be "hundreds of semantic fields at the lexical level".

Below is the combination of some terms belonging to the adjective word group to a certain semantic field:

1. Adjectives denoting different characteristics:

1.1. Adjectives denoting the characteristics of people: badniyat, khudkomona, chapson (chapson), durri nosufta, madadkor, kalapatra, kushtigir, kajbahs, atashafza, purg'am, goratgir, siniqdil, hozik, zafarqarin, addoi, mufsid, korfarmo, gaddor, badkor, cattal and etc.

We turn to the examples. Let the governor himself know about Badniyat and Humroh Mavlonozada's selfish actions, and let him know and take measures! (S.) When they chased after each other, it became clear that the killer had settled in Barakai Ghuryan area. (U.S.) The owners did not see these things! (U.S.) The next is a state-loving city - a city whose people are accustomed to rule, eager to enslave others, but they themselves do not want to bow down to anyone.

(U.S.) Fakhriddin Mahmud alias Ibn Yamin was an eloquent person. Shahriyor thinks that Etti Pusty may have had an ancestor of dervish behavior and poetic nature. (S.) I didn't know that the emirs of the nation were so angry! This citizen, avomunnos Amir Husayn, is very sick of politics. (S.) The slaves mocked the fool who robbed the faith in their hearts. (S.) Without the kingship, the victorious brave people of Samarkand came face to face with the evil and cruel soldiers. (S.) It is necessary to cut the roots of corrupt communities...

(U.S.) The noblest of the amirs, the beloved liver of the master, Jahangir Mirza, was very happy about the swiftness in the war. (U.S.)

1.2. Adjectives denoting the different characteristics of things-subjects: munaqkash (patterned), qabal bilad, fagfuri, gardunkudrat, yalakat, humoyunnishan, o'trik, murassa', rabbani, bashukuh, chalchik, pistoqi, forom, chinakchi, tabdili, misqoli, bebadal, abtarin, razim -lobid, gharqabli, obdor, piskin, khirpa, sultani, shavqiyab. There are many types of ignorant cities.

The first is a necessary city... (S.) The treatise contains the valuable works of Arastu, al-Farabi, Abu Ali Sina... (S.) Kunduzak, Sovg'onchi, Kumushkent, Vidar, Khartang, Khojai Kalon located around Samarkand, The situation is not completely different in all Chinese villages like Sogorch and Khoja Gunjora. (S.) At that time, he liked something about the boy Tokhtamysh, apparently, he liked to behave arrogantly in front of others, to care for those around him. (U.S.) After a short skirmish, they switched to javelin fighting, but nothing came out of the pistachio spears. - Master! (U.S.)

2. Lexemes denoting color: purple, oloyi. The light blue dress on her sleeve, the purple robe covering her waist showed all the elegance of the princess, and the wind played with the red silk scarf on her head... (U.s.)

3. Historical lexemes denoting shape and volume:

Fuzun, Kotoh, Dongil, Poydor, Obdor, Biyla, Chaldevor, Takhtiravon, Kulohnamo, Rasida. Qutlug Turkon, who was happy to see the height of the princes, met them all, starting with Jahangir Mirzo...

(U.S.) Uchqur was a strong, flying horse, he loves all kinds of wide fields. (U.S.) The word obdor in this sentence is a Persian word and means the following:

1. tramp. 2. maj. Clear, pure; shiny In the quoted passage, the word obdor is used figuratively.

4. Historical lexemes denoting taste: nakuli. Who tasted the delicious food as a snack, and who reached for the plate. (S.) "Nuql" is explained as follows: "Nuql is a sweet, fruit and other kind of food eaten when drinking May." In the above sentence, we assume that nuql is used in the conditional case in the sense of sweet, delicious.

5. Historical lexemes expressing the meaning of status: uryan, faqir, poor, shabgir, zakhdor, mustahiq, kamgak, nigun, sarnigun, zuptagina, muvahhid (muvahhad), zabun, ismat, hamogush, atashnok. - If he is a monogamist, then he can get married without difficulty, he can get married! - the imam said this. (S.) Inchunin, in the noble city, according to the belief of the warlord, there is no warlord, nor a sarnigun, everyone has equal rights... (S.) El-ulus is in the place of a slave, maybe even more nigun... (S.) For now, it was an imaginary community of poor people, runudu avbosh, made up of dreams and thoughts. (S.) The saint, who relied on God, often fell into a state of ecstasy due to the fervor of his love, and the sound of takbirs, which were spoken with enthusiasm, could be heard even in the street. (U.S.) In revealing the poetic features of Muhammad Ali's novels "Warlords" and "The Great Kingdom", the role of historical linguistic units representing the meanings of signs and characteristics among the linguistic units

belonging to different semantic field is great in the reflection of real reality and the provision of artistry.

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